

Report on the NZ Species edit-a-thon 2024

By Heidi Meudt ([0000-0002-2433-9071](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2433-9071)), Siobhan Leachman ([0000-0002-5398-7721](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5398-7721)) and Christine Richardson

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New Zealand Species Edit-a-thon 19 October & 2 November 2024

Slide 1 of the NZ Species Edit-a-thon slidedeck, by Siobhan Leachman and Heidi Meudt 2024. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Event details

Organisers: Christine Richardson (CR [User:Noracrentiss](#)), Siobhan Leachman (SL [User:Ambrosia10](#)), and Heidi Meudt (HM [User:Stitchbird2](#))

Support: Mike Dickison (MD [User:Giantflightlessbirds](#))

Venue: Ōtari-Wilton's Bush, Wellington, New Zealand

Dates: 19 October and 2 November, 2024

Theme: New Zealand species

Aims: Onboarding and upskilling new Wikipedia editors, improving Wikipedia articles about NZ species, adding species images to Wikimedia Commons, and widen the network of the Wiki editing community in Wellington

Organisation

Planning meetings

The organisers (CR, SL and HM) had been informally discussing the idea of a NZ species edit-a-thon for several months. At the August 2024 Wellington Wiki meetup, CR and HM decided to set up a meeting with SL to start organising the edit-a-thon. Once the three organisers committed to running this edit-a-thon, regular weekly meetings were established using zoom from 10 September 2024. A [Google doc](#) was used to keep notes during meetings and to track the accomplishment of organisational tasks. Google docs and sheets were also used for the creation of resources needed for the edit-a-thon such as the introductory slide deck. A [Google folder](#) was also created to assist with the organisation of all the documents associated with the edit-a-thon. All planning and logistics were accomplished in six weeks.

A WhatsApp group was established to provide an easy channel of communication for organisers. This worked well and ensured organisers were kept up to date on developments outside of the formal Zoom meetings. We also held additional meetings, to synchronously prepare resources or continue important discussions, where required.

Marketing and communications

The organisers created a [Wikipedia edit-a-thon event page](#) on Wiki and used this to assist with outreach and event advertising. We used ChatGPT to assist with the creation and refinement of marketing text for the event. We also created a [Wikimedia Commons category](#) to assist with the organisation of media and images created for and during the edit-a-thon.

The marketing of this event was strategic with the organisers reaching out via email to a variety of potentially interested groups and people. We used our own contacts in the local, regional and national scientific and citizen science communities to spread the word. We wrote short articles for the NZ Plant Conservation Network newsletter, the Glean Report, and the Royal Society Bulletin Alert. The Wellington Gardens team at Wellington City Council also promoted our events on their social media pages, and encouraged us to make short videos ([one by HM](#) and [one by SL](#)) inviting people to our event. These “reels” were shared via Facebook and Instagram. We also uploaded the reels into the above Wikimedia Commons category.

The organisers felt that although they did their best, the communication strategy could have been improved with the advice of a specialist in this area.

Funding

A [funding application](#) was made to Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand, which was successful. These funds covered catering for two full days, giveaways for the participants (e.g. bags and stickers), and a donation to Ōtari-Wilton’s Bush Trust. Wellington City Council allowed us to use the Leonard Cockayne Centre (and its wifi) as our venue for free on both days of the

event, which significantly decreased our costs. They also supported us by bringing several books from their library for us to use at the event.

Day 1: Saturday 19 October 2024

Introduction

People were warmly welcomed to the Leonard Cockayne Centre venue at Ōtari-Wilton's Bush on arrival around 10 am by CR, SL, HM and MD. Tea, coffee and biscuits were available on arrival and on a help-yourself basis all day. Including the organisers, we were a total of 15 people participating on Day 1 of the edit-a-thon.

After the karakia, there was a round of self-introductions. This included asking participants to say what their favourite New Zealand species was. The purpose of this was to provide an opportunity not just for the participants to introduce themselves but also to provide an icebreaker and to give organisers an indication of areas of interest for editing. CR wrote names and favourite species up on the whiteboard as an aid to helping learn people's names. Unfortunately the organisers failed to provide name tags or lanyards for attendees. The organisers recommend stickers or lanyards be provided for participants to add their name and Wikipedia user name and attach to themselves.

A brief [slide deck presentation](#) was given by the organisers to give participants housekeeping information, to introduce the new editors to Wikipedia and to assist them in learning how to edit.

Content (morning)

It was then time to ensure that the new editors were trained in how to edit Wikipedia. We were lucky in that there were nearly even numbers of experienced editors to new. This resulted in the new editors being tutored one-on-one.

While SL and HM were assisting new editors without an account to sign up, CR ensured that all participants had been added to the Day 1 Dashboard. SL attempted to ensure all new editors had a welcome on their talk page.

Lunch break

We took on board a recommendation from Lucy Schrader following the [Te Papa Exhibitions Edit-a-thon](#) in July 2024 which was to "enforce" a set time for a break for lunch. We were fortunate to have a lovely outdoor space immediately outside the Centre as well as a beautiful sunny day. This meant participants spent time talking to each other which helped create a sense of community and collaboration.

[Selfie of the 15 participants at Day 1 of the 2024 NZ species edit-a-thon](#). Mike Dickison, [CC BY 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Content (afternoon)

Geoff Ridley, a board member of the Ōtari-Wilton's Bush Trust and a fellow attendee at the edit-a-thon, gave a short presentation welcoming edit-a-thon editors to Ōtari-Wilton's Bush. He also shared a history of the Reserve as well as further information on his ongoing engagement with the same.

After his presentation, the edit-a-thon participants were encouraged to continue to edit.

Wrap Up

At the conclusion of the day, HM and SL wrapped up with a very short slide session reminding participants of the time, date and location of Day 2 of the edit-a-thon, information on resources supporting editing, providing email addresses to enable participants to reach out for support. Time was then given to attendees to fill in the event survey. The organisers also elicited an informal discussion and feedback on how attendees thought the day had gone with the aim of planning and improving Day 2 of the edit-a-thon.

Finally the organisers encouraged participants to become a member of [Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand \(WANZ\)](#). A karakia was said to close the day.

[Busy editors on Day 1](#). Heidi Meudt, [CC BY 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

General comments

The ratio of experienced to newbie editors meant the newbies got a lot of individual and specific attention. We received [survey responses from all 12 attendees](#) who were not organisers. Feedback and comments were very positive. It appeared most people had found the day valuable and enjoyable, with all attendees saying they were well satisfied or very much satisfied with the event, and that Wikipedia editing is relevant or very relevant to them personally.

In their own words, they learned technical skills such as “how to edit Wikipedia articles”, “how to edit, add links, add headings, and add and change images”, “how to attach photos in infoboxes and use Wikimedia Commons”, and even “improvement of all skills”. The attendees also appreciated the social aspects of the event, stating “how amazing the community is”, that it was an “awesome supportive environment”, and that they “learned how exciting all this is!!”

It also appeared that editor confidence was boosted, as one commented they were pleased to discover “that I could edit fauna pages!” Finally, 10 of 12 attendees said they were highly likely to edit Wikipedia in future, join a local Wikimedia community, or attend other Wiki events in future, suggesting that there is enthusiasm and that they will become active editors.

Would you like to attend more Wikipedia edit-a-thons, workshops, meet-ups or conferences?

12 responses

Visualisation generated from the Google survey created by the organisers. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Day 2: Saturday 2 November 2024

Introduction

On Day 2 the organisers were extremely gratified to see the high number of repeat attendees from Day 1. The attendees were again warmly welcomed to the Leonard Cockayne Centre venue at Ōtari-Wilton's Bush. Again, tea, coffee and biscuits were available both on arrival and on a help-yourself basis all day. Including the organisers, there were a total of 12 people participating on Day 2 of the edit-a-thon, with all attendees having also attended Day 1.

Content (morning)

A brief [slide deck presentation](#) was given by the organisers to give participants housekeeping information and to answer questions raised during the informal feedback session at the end of Day 1 as well as questions raised when attendees answered the formal feedback survey (Question: What topics would you like covered (or reviewed) on Day 2...). The organisers viewed this as a satisfactory way to commence the day as attendees were able raise further issues they had been having while editing during the two weeks between edit-a-thon event days.

Lunch

Again the organisers "enforced" a set time for a break for lunch. The organisers believed this break definitely helped with productivity and also encouraged the collegial atmosphere of the edit-a-thon.

[Some of the editors on Day 2](#). Mike Dickison, [CC BY 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Content (afternoon)

After lunch HM and SL again gave a very brief [slide deck presentation](#) giving attendees information on the afternoon session. We explained that MD would take a subsection of attendees off into Ōtari-Wilton's Bush to teach them photographic techniques and then return to the venue to educate interested attendees how to upload images they had taken into Wikimedia Commons and reuse the same in Wikipedia.

Those editors who stayed behind continued to edit various Wikipedia pages.

Wrap up

Prior to the close of the day, the HM and SL gave a final slide deck presentation giving attendees information on tools that could be used to upload research-grade openly licensed iNaturalist images into Wikicommons. HM and SL also addressed the issue of what editors should do if they have questions after the edit-a-thon. In the penultimate slide the organisers gave attendees guidance on getting further involved in the Wikimedia movement including how to join WANZ and how to attend in-person and virtual meetups.

A karakia was then said and Day 2 of the edit-a-thon was complete.

General comments

Numbers were slightly fewer than on Day 1. Including the organisers, there were a total of 12 people participating on Day 2 of the edit-a-thon. One person was sick, another had

previously flagged a prior commitment. We were very pleased with the high percentage of people who attended Day 1 and then returned two weeks later for Day 2 of the event. One person had to leave at lunchtime because of a prior commitment.

We received [survey responses from five attendees](#) who were not organisers. Feedback and comments were again very positive. It appeared most people had found Day 2 to be valuable and enjoyable, with all attendees saying they were very much satisfied with the event.

Do you feel you built upon your Wikipedia knowledge and skills in day 2 of the event?

4 responses

Visualisation generated from the Google survey created by the organisers. [CC BY 4.0](#)

On Day 2, attendees told us they learned additional technical skills such as “how to be a better editor”, “where to go to get help and resources”, “how references and infoboxes work”, and even “Wikidata stuff!” All attendees felt that they built upon their Wikipedia knowledge and skills on Day 2. They liked the format of the event over two Saturdays, which gave them useful time to practice editing in between and which meant they didn’t have to give up an entire weekend. Again, the community aspect was highlighted in the comments, e.g. “Such a beautiful community, welcoming, collaborative. Food was delicious too,” and “Great day, great venue, great people.”

Thinking now about BOTH days of the NZ edit-a-thon, How did you find out about the edit-a-thon?

Tick all that apply.

5 responses

Visualisation generated from the Google survey created by the organisers. [CC BY 4.0](#).

Finally, we asked how they found out about the event, which may be helpful information for future events (although admittedly the sample size is quite small).

Impact

Metrics

Two dashboards were created, one for [Day 1](#) and one for [Day 2](#), to track the contributions of editors. As reported in the [WANZ blog on the edit-a-thon](#) a total of 52,230 words were added, 44 new articles were created, 142 articles were edited and 448 references were added. The organisers were gratified to see from these dashboards that the aim of 100 Wikipedia articles improved as stated in the funding application to WANZ was well exceeded.

Post-Event Activity

A donation of \$250 was made to Ōtari-Wilton's Bush Trust per our Budget request. Several tote bags were donated to staff at OTWB.

The organisers reported back to the wider Wiki communities on these edit-a-thons, i.e. [the GLAMwiki newsletter](#), and the Wellington and Aotearoa New Zealand Wiki meetups.

Recommendations

Prior to the event

- Grant applications to WANZ should not include a “scholarships” line. These are handled directly by WANZ via another mechanism.
- If offering “waived WANZ membership fees” to attendees, clear communication is required with the Treasurer and also in comms to attendees. (*Membership is not automatic*).
- Provide ticketing through WANZ's Humanitix account, noting that WANZ will receive the ticket income directly. A decision needs to be made on whether to “absorb” ticketing fees or to add them to the purchase price. Recommend absorbing fees.
- Increase WANZ understanding and skills of use of Humanitix functionality for comms and marketing.
- Work with the new WANZ Communications Advisor to develop a clear comms strategy for the event.
- Create video clips to put on social media as early as possible.
- Consider what merch/giveaway is suitable for the event and purchase it in advance.

At the event

- Ensure venue wifi is adequate for a large group.
- Make catering “all vegetarian” as this helps to simplify meeting any dietary requirements.
- Have a roll-along case for taking WANZ gear to a venue.
- Have a WANZ banner/signage that is adaptable to the outdoors, especially for the Wellington wind!
- Have name stickers and Sharpies in the WANZ case for people to use at events to help attendees remember names and create a friendly space.
- Create a Google survey for your event. Organisers obtained valuable insights from attendees filling out both the Day 1 and Day 2 surveys.
- Assign administrative tasks, such as assisting with Dashboard sign ups and welcoming new editors to Wikipedia, to a non presenting organiser.

Administrative aspects

Welcoming new editors

SL received feedback from [User:Schwede66](#) that the [New Zealand welcome template](#) should be used i.e. `{{welcome-nz}}` ~~~~ when welcoming new editors participating in a New Zealand- edit-a-thon. SL had added a general welcome template as this was the quickest and easiest to find at the time, given the time constraints of the edit-a-thon. In order to help ensure the more specific New Zealand welcome is used it is recommended that, like the task of ensuring everyone is added to the event dashboard, this task is also assigned to an organiser who is not presenting and training during the edit-a-thon.

Venue

Leonard Cockayne Centre was an excellent choice for 15 people. If we had had 25 people, it would have been very tight.

- information on how to access the venue was delivered in a timely manner
- wifi was excellent
- TV and cables were all provided
- trestle tables were extremely heavy - but therefore very stable
- mobility access was good
- there was good access to electrical outlets, toilets and kitchen facilities
- Ōtari’s library was made available
- there was excellent access to plant and animal species outside

Ticketing

Humanitix proved to be an excellent platform for ticketing although it was a bit tricky to set up one event on two separate days with one price covering both sessions. It has more functionality than we used in the area of marketing and comms. Humanitix tickets payments

were put through the WANZ account. We opted to absorb the ticketing fees which reduced the income slightly.

Catering

Angie Stainer of Chefgirl and Bar Boy (chefgirlandbarboy@gmail.com) provided excellent delicious and varied food for both sessions. Quantities were just right. Because of the small size of the fridge at the venue, we opted for delivery just before lunch. Consequently, morning tea items were purchased separately.

We ordered 100% vegetarian to simplify dietary requirements a bit. In fact, Angie also provided vegan options. She seems to prefer to communicate by text.

WANZ gear

CR collected a well-stocked container of WANZ gear (multi-boards, extension cables, stationery, first aid kit, etc.) from Dianne Skelton's home a few days prior to the event. Everything we required was included and we were very happy to find in the box a roll of gaffer tape which solved a safety problem around cabling on the floor. The container is heavy and a bit unwieldy and we understand a roll-along suitcase is to be purchased.

The WANZ banners were erected but were found to be rather unstable in the Wellington wind. We therefore erected one inside the room facing out through a window but few passers-by would have seen it. The organisers of the edit-a-thon recommend replacing these when appropriate with banners that are more adaptable to the Wellington wind.

Giveaways

A range of WANZ stickers was provided in the box of gear. These were popular with attendees.

We considered getting designed bookmarks but the number of attendees was insufficient to warrant the expense of a designer and minimum quantity to order. We suggested that WANZ look into purchasing a somewhat generic range of WANZ bookmarks for distribution at any events held around the country.

Instead of bookmarks, we chose to purchase tote bags on which an image from Commons of beetle was printed (with correct attribution!). The quality of the tote bags was somewhat disappointing, however. We gave one to every attendee and also left several at Ōtari-Wiltons Bush for staff and trustees. Leftover bags are to be returned to WANZ.

Fifteen cards with pencil sketches of native trees were purchased and given out to attendees with the tote bag. CR created a page of images of the participants' "favourite species" which was included in each tote bag.

Finances

The Edit-a-thon came in well under budget and unspent funds have been returned to WANZ. A link to the Budget and reconciliation is [here](#).

Future work

MD proposed holding a similar species edit-a-thon in or around Christchurch.

SL & HM are discussing the possibility of holding another species edit-a-thon in the first quarter/half of 2025.